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Map kinase inhibition and cancer immunity.

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We modeled short and long term transcriptional responses to MAP kinase inhibition in melanoma and in colorectal cancer cells *in vitro* using whole transcriptome technologies.

1 Results

- 2 a. Silencing of NGFR is a primary transcriptional consequence of trametinib kinase inhibition.
3 i. NGFR is a receptor type integrating TNFR and EGFR family signals.
4 b. Identification of an ETS factor selectively silenced by trametinib, *ELF3*.
5 c. Compensatory oncogene activation is prominent with trametinib.
6 i. Etv1 activation
7 ii. Etv4 activation

8 Immunoregulatory effects of trametinib were not appreciable in this cellular system (A375) likely due to
9 time frame of observation (24 hours) and technical matters related to cell culture.

10 We studied a second culture model of human cancer using RNA-sequencing to monitor the cellular
11 response system-wide. Here, we harnessed the power of integration of findings from three separate cell
12 culture models:

13 GSE265926

- 14 a. Nuclear transport is halted by trametinib.
15 i. Kapb1 silencing
16 ii. Loss of Ran
17 iii. Nup153 silencing
18 iv. Loss of RanBP1
19 b. Immunologic aspects of trametinib kinase inhibition.
20 i. Lrig2 activation.
21 ii. Vsr activation.
22 iii. Igbp1 activation.
23 iv. Igfn1 activation
24 v. Pdc4 induction.
25 1. Immunologic aspects of cell death
26 vi. Activation of catalase.
27 1. Cytotoxic effector functions
28 vii. Activation of *CD59*.
viii. Effective silencing of the interferon related developmental gene *IFRD2*
ix. cGAS and Sting1 were not affected by trametinib here but we observed weak induction of RIG-I and MAVS.
x. Induction of CCL26 and CCL15 in cancer cells exposed to trametinib.
xi. Activation of receptor subunits for tolerogenic cytokines IL-3, IL-10 and IL-17 (IL3RA, IL10RB, IL-17RC and IL-17RE) but with loss of tolerogenic IL-27RA.

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2 c. Ubiquitin in cancer.

- 3 i. Trametinib silences UBE2T, UBE2I and UBE2N

4 d. EGR/IER signaling module in cancer.

- 5 i. Trametinib treatment silences EGR1 signaling

6 e. Transformation is broadly affected by trametinib.

- 7 i. Trametinib silences the stem loop binding protein, SLBP.
8 ii. Trametinib silences TCP1.
9 iii. Trametinib silences ILF3.
iv. Trametinib silences UNG.

10 f. Tumor suppression is engaged by trametinib.

- 11 i. Tp53inp1 induction

12 g. Compensatory responses involving nutrient sensing are evident with MAP kinase inhibition.

- 13 i. TSR1 rebound activation
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15 Discussion

16 We presented here multiple lines of transcriptomic evidence demonstrating likely chemotherapeutic benefit
17 of MAP kinase inhibition with trametinib in human cancer cells. We focused here on an interesting aspect
18 of MAP kinase inhibition with relevance to cancer therapy involving immunomodulatory properties of
19 kinase inhibitors.
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Citations

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